

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SCALE OF THE VIEWING ANGLE IN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract. Analysis of solutions to the problem of students' ability to choose the right distance and the correct setting of the viewing angle in relation to the field of view.

Keywords: field of view, angle of view, object, eye contact, scale, distance, horizon line, horizontal position, plein air, space, image, spatial perspective.

The field of view and angle of view is the coverage of the object depicted by the artist at the time of viewing. As the imaged object moves away, the field of view expands, which makes it possible to clearly see and describe all parts of the imaged object (Fig. 1, 2). But, standing at a great distance from the object, it is very difficult to fully describe all its parts and volumes.

On the contrary, all parts of this object are difficult to see even at a close distance from the depicted object. The ability to choose the right distance and correctly determine the field of view requires skill from the artist. In many cases, artists paint at a distance equal to 3 times the size of the subject being depicted.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Image Scale

For example, in order to fully depict the human figure, the artist must stand at a distance of approximately 5-5.5 meters from nature. Only then will he be able to fully imagine the image and accurately complete the task. On fig. 1.2 shows how far the artist stands from the tree to depict it. In figure 3 we see the scale in the image, and in figure 4 we see a way to determine the height of a person along the horizon line in perspective.

Figure 3
Skyline

The horizon line is the light passing through the eye level. We can determine the horizon by lifting the paper horizontally to eye level.

1. Above the horizon line.
2. Below the horizon line.
3. At the height of the light of our eyes (at the height of the horizon line).

The horizon line always passes through the height of the eye. If we go up, then it will rise with us, if we go down, then the horizon will also go down (Fig. 5 a, b).

Picture 4

On fig. 5 shows a plein air view above and below the horizon.

Figure 6 below shows the position of the bookshelf floors relative to the horizon line.

Figure 5

Figure 6

Spatial perspective

Spatial perspective means that things change (shrink) under the influence of space. Space is a transparent medium. But its transparency can change under the influence of various natural phenomena. For example: air humidity, changes in atmospheric pressure, the influence of air dustiness, cloudiness, etc. Therefore, the way the depicted object is located in space has a strong influence on the color, proportions, tone and appearance of its individual parts (bright or soft).

The spatial perspective changes depending on the time of day (morning, afternoon, evening), season (spring, summer, autumn) and atmospheric changes (sunny or cloudy).

There are several basic rules for spatial perspective, namely:

1. Objects close to the artist are obvious, while distant objects are generally visible. To perceive the space in the image, it is necessary to clearly describe objects that are at close range, and distant in a general way.

2. Objects located in space (in width) look dimmer the farther they are from the artist. In order to correctly convey the spatial perspective in the image, objects located in the distance should be somewhat lighter, and objects in the foreground should be clearly depicted.

3. Objects located at a close distance seem to be distinctly voluminous in space, and distant objects seem dimmer. It is also necessary to follow this procedure when imaging.

4. Objects located farther from the artist appear inky, airy and pale under the influence of atmospheric pressure. In order to show the perspective of space more strongly, it is necessary to clearly depict objects that are clearly visible at close range, and those that are far away in a lighter color.

Figure 7

5. Objects in the first row have their true color (color), and objects in the distance are the same. This law of spatial perspective requires the artist to depict objects that are at close range, clearly, and objects that are at a distance, generally more fuzzy.

Compliance with these laws of spatial perspective is very important for students. The student must comply with the above rules, regardless of what task he performs (portrait, still life, landscape, etc.).

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